

New models of participatory process

SPOKE 4 – Digital and Sustainable Mountain

DELIVERABLE 1 INTERFACEUNIBAS

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In Research Module 2 (Flagship 3 – INTERFACE – “Competitiveness of Economic Activities and Enhancement of Natural and Cultural Assets in Mountain and Remote Areas”), research and experimental activities are developed aimed at designing digital strategies for the enhancement of natural and cultural itineraries in various case studies in the

mountainous areas of Basilicata. Specifically, this contribution summarizes the establishment of a process for the collection and critical analysis of data involving local digital enterprises and potential users, both residents and tourists, capable of generating a model of shared digital knowledge. This facilitates the emergence of active citizenship, which is essential in communities with high dispersion.

A) Citizen engagement, data collection and literature review

Introduction

In recent years, Basilicata has only slightly strengthened its capacity to generate innovation. This outcome is attributed to significant actions by the public research system on one hand, and a very modest contribution from businesses on the other. Naturally, the small organizational size, with an inevitable deficit in critical mass, limited sectoral heterogeneity predominantly traditional and low-tech activities and a propensity for collaboration more out of obligation than choice hinder Lucanian companies from covering a wide range of technological domains. Furthermore, the small size makes it more difficult for businesses to express a demand for innovation and to stimulate collaborative opportunities with the public research sector (Source: “S3 Smart Specialization Strategy” 2021-2027 Basilicata). On the other hand, the tourism sector appears to be central, having experienced significant growth in demand flows and supply structures in recent years. However, this growth is concentrated almost exclusively in the southeastern part of Basilicata (Matera and the Ionian coast), driven by the momentum from the Matera 2019 event. Therefore, there is a need to build upon this positive experience to enhance the quality of the regional tourism offering, aligning cultural content with new technologies to more effectively represent the environmental and landscape quality of the region and to improve the enjoyment of tangible and intangible cultural heritage through innovative services. Conversely, considering Basilicata’s share of investment in R&D, it appears marginal in absolute terms, reflecting the small size of the region and its businesses. According to the latest available ISTAT data released at the end of 2022, intramural R&D expenditures in Basilicata in 2020 were just over 77.5 million euros, of which over 40% is attributed to public institutions (excluding universities) and only 18% to the business sector (**Table 1**).

Area territoriale	Imprese	Istituzioni pubbliche	Università	Istituzioni private non profit	Totale
Basilicata	18.115	31.474	27.679	305	77.573
Mezzogiorno	1.193.172	376.791	1.013.298	37.486	2.620.747
Italia	15.467.164	3.306.741	5.777.890	476.462	25.028.257

Table 1. R&D Expenditure in Basilicata, the Mezzogiorno, and Italy in 2020 in thousands of euros. Source: ISTAT data processed and included in S3 2021-2027 Basilicata.

In summary, the analysis highlights the fragilities of the examined sectors, primarily based on data collection efforts and a review of relevant literature, with a particular focus on the “Smart Specialization Strategy (S3) 2021-2027” for the Basilicata region. The second phase of the activities shifted toward the active involvement of citizens and businesses.

For citizen engagement, the research group, within the framework of Module M2, organized various events and individual meetings with stakeholders, especially in areas that appear more disadvantaged, such as remote and mountainous regions. Specifically, the involvement of residents in the Internal SNAI area “Montagna Materana” (comprising 8 municipalities) as a symbolic case study of the fragility of Lucanian internal areas revealed several levels of inadequacy in digital infrastructure concerning services for citizens. Furthermore, direct experiences with local citizens/users of the cultural tourism sector and public administration conducted over a 4-month period in the 8 municipalities (Accettura, Aliano, Cirigliano, Craco, Gorgoglione, San Mauro Forte, Oliveto Lucano, Stigliano) culminated in a public concluding workshop held on October 24, 2024, titled “Southern Roadshow: Ideas and Projects for Innovation and Sustainability in Motion,” involving local businesses. The event, held at the Macchia Romana campus of the University of Basilicata in Potenza, included presentations, roundtables, poster sessions, and pitches from the winning companies of the cascading NODES “Line A Mezzogiorno” calls, which showcased the projects and the initial results achieved so far. This meeting served as a useful platform for igniting new connections among the key players of change and innovation.

Main findings

- Support for activities aimed at engaging citizens to include the contributions of stakeholders in the analysis of the regional context and innovation potential.
- Support for knowledge enhancement, through citizen involvement, of new digital solutions, content, and technological tools useful for discovering and enhancing local heritage.
- Increased operational engagement of businesses in key sectors of Basilicata, starting with tourism, to support entire supply chains (Workshops, Cascading Calls “Line A Mezzogiorno”).
- Support for territories in seeking new models of welfare and entrepreneurial development, experimenting with more sustainable forms of tourism and new entrepreneurial trajectories linked to cultural and creative sectors.
- Understanding the dynamics related to the development of businesses in the Mezzogiorno concerning tourism and culture (e.g., regional clusters).

Conclusions

The research activities conducted thus highlight the need to act through transformative processes and models of community engagement, supported by technologies for territory mapping, smart mobility, IoT, and integrated digital platforms. This approach is particularly essential for marginal, smaller, and mountainous areas and also involves the engagement of transient communities, such as non-resident citizens participating in slow and sustainable tourism. At the core of these needs are information technologies, open data, as well as user-centered design processes and community co-design methodologies, and design for self-empowerment to create opportunities for sustainable development. This approach enhances community identity, counteracts depopulation processes, and promotes access to decision-making processes in territories, as well as facilitating access to basic services.

Bibliography

1. Regione Basilicata, “S3 Smart Specialisation Strategy” 2021-2027 Basilicata. Link: <https://europa.regione.basilicata.it/2021-27/programma/s3-smart-specialisation-strategy/>

B) A new model of participatory process

Introduction

Based on the information gathered in section A, a new model of participatory process has been outlined, including some suggestions for best practices for the mountainous areas of Basilicata and, more generally, for the mountainous areas of Southern Italy.

The model

The developed model suggests some general guidelines on the possibility of reducing the peripheral status of mountainous areas primarily through participatory engagement, in order to ensure more effective accessibility to services. The model, as structured, investigates the following fundamental elements:

- The importance of optimizing digital infrastructures even in essential services. Improving access to technology and digital literacy can help reduce poverty by promoting economic and social inclusion. The digitization of services enables the overcoming of geographical barriers that limit access to opportunities and resources. For example, e-commerce can help local small businesses reach a broader market, allowing them to sell their products beyond regional borders. Digital solutions can also enhance the quality of life in internal areas: from e-learning, which enables young people to access quality educational pathways without having to leave their territory, to telemedicine, which ensures healthcare availability even in under-served areas.
- The role of digitization as an important aggregative and engagement function in mountainous and rural areas, aimed at creating “smart villages” where the number of implemented technologies is less important than how they are utilized to support the community itself. Among the initiatives to be implemented is the creation of public-private foundations that promote the establishment of start-ups and businesses in mountainous areas and work on attracting and utilizing funds to enhance digitalization in these areas.
- The improvement of infrastructural conditions and connectivity between mountain municipalities, including car sharing, especially car-pooling, and on-demand collective taxi systems, which can facilitate mobility and accessibility in territories without generating high costs. This is especially relevant in areas with very low housing density.
- Another dimension is the need for sustainable mobility and better physical connectivity between territories. The circulation of people and goods is a crucial aspect of social and economic development and cohesion, requiring significant investments to achieve equitable growth; these investments must be closely aligned with the energy and ecological transitions.
- The implementation of remote work, for instance, can be extremely beneficial in preventing depopulation of mountainous areas and the closure of local businesses; the mountainous territories of Basilicata, due to their beauty, could attract hybrid or remote workers.
- Attention to essential services, primarily related to health, with the introduction of digital infrastructures such as telemedicine. This can be achieved through remote consultations with doctors, allowing residents to access efficient social and health services locally.
- In-depth exploration of the education theme. The work conducted highlights significant challenges related to multi-classrooms, which have emerged as a response to the reduced number of students. At the same time, they have

proven effective for the learning of children and young people, also promoting the acquisition of certain skills, such as relational abilities, compared to traditional classes.

Conclusions

The great challenge for Italian mountain communities, especially in the Mezzogiorno, is the need to bridge the gap in telecommunications that still separates them from major cities. Only this infrastructural innovation, resulting from a joint effort between the public and private sectors, can enable the implementation of state-of-the-art solutions for tourism. New technologies play a key role in creating memorable experiences that connect visitors with the cultural heritage of mountain communities while also making these areas safer and better serviced for both tourists and residents. In light of this, the research activities conducted develop various proposals for innovation in territorial systems through a “participatory model,” aimed at enhancing the lifestyle associated with digitalization in mountain communities. Digitalization holds enormous potential to transform life and opportunities in rural and remote areas. Our experience has shown that digitalization can overcome physical distances to provide opportunities and services, regardless of where we live, as long as we have good digital connectivity.